

EXPEDITION REPORT

Expedition dates:

1 – 13 September 2024 | 6 – 19 September 2025

Report published:

March 2026

From elephants to cats to butterflies: Monitoring Biodiversity of Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve, Malawi

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Authors:

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**Matthias Hammer (editor)
Biosphere Expeditions**

ABSTRACT

In September 2024 and 2025, Biosphere Expeditions' citizen scientists supported research activities conducted by Lilongwe Wildlife Trust (LWT) in Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve (VMWR) for the fifth and sixth year running since 2018 (excluding COVID years 2020 and 2021) This combined 2024/2025 report presents comparative 2024/2025 data, as well as across all six expeditions, to examine ecological changes in VMWR.

Data collected during the annual Biosphere Expeditions projects in VMWR have been invaluable in monitoring biodiversity and megafauna population levels. Elephant populations appear to be stable and not consuming cultivated crops. Hippo populations have dramatically declined over the past six years and the reasons for this decline should be investigated and management strategies developed in partnership with Nyika-Vwaza Co-Management Trust (NVCMT). The expedition so far has been limited to one or more groups during the dry season. It is recommended to replicate the expedition work during other seasons, potentially bi-annually, to assess seasonality of these results. Group-specific results were:

Elephant herd sightings and dung sampling: Across Malawi, conflict between humans and elephants *Loxodonta africana* - when elephants leave protected areas and enter community- or farm-land - has become an increasing threat to human livelihoods. This in turn is a threat to elephants, which are at risk of retaliatory attacks when they forage on crops. In 2021, a fence was erected along the southern and eastern boundaries of Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve (VMWR) in an attempt to keep the elephants inside the reserve. In 2025 citizen scientists recorded 323 elephants in 38 sightings (four solo males and 34 herds) inside VMWR. This was low compared to most previous years apart from 2023. However, the decline over time was not statistically significant. Citizen scientists also added one new elephant ID to the LWT elephant database and updated three existing IDs. 146 dung boli samples were also collected and their seed content analysed to assess which plant species elephants feed on and whether crops are being consumed. No evidence of crop consumption was found, despite recent reports of elephants leaving the park. This was consistent with previous years.

Hippo transects: *Hippopotamus amphibius* teeth are a source of ivory, making this species susceptible to poaching. Within VMWR, Lake Kazuni and the southern section of the Rukuru River are the only permanent water sources and therefore primary areas for hippos. Monitoring them is essential and Biosphere Expeditions' annual monitoring is the only effort of this kind. The expedition completed six transects along the northern lakeside, which resulted in 502 hippos being counted. The largest single transect count was 114. The hippo population trend in VMWR has statistically significantly decreased over time, with peaks in 2018 and 2019 and the lowest counts in 2024. There was a population increase from 2024 to 2025. However, this was still much lower than 2018 and 2019 levels. The reasons for this decline are as yet unknown.

Camera trapping: Camera traps are a non-invasive way to monitor biodiversity and detect elusive and shy species, which may not be otherwise detected. 14 camera traps were deployed by the expedition along the two main roads within the reserve (the main track and northern track), as well as six at sites of animal activity, such as mammal paths, along the lakeside and airstrip. Over 264 camera trap nights, the cameras recorded 2835 animal photos of 24 species with hippos recorded the most (972 photos over 95 captures). Other noteworthy species included leopard *Panthera pardus*, serval *Leptailurus serval* and side-striped jackal *Lupulella adusta*. Results were consistent with previous years, and the number of species captured over the expeditions did not differ significantly.

Bird transects: Birds are an excellent indicator of overall ecosystem health, particularly aquatic birds. VMWR has sporadically monitored bird diversity in the past, but records have not been updated recently so this activity was added to update records. The expedition conducted four bird transects along the northern section of the lakeside and recorded 42 species over 85 sightings.

Night transects: Nocturnal mammals are elusive and difficult to monitor. To complement the camera trapping study and make biodiversity assessments more robust, the expedition conducted four evening/early morning driving transects around the southern area of VMWR, recording any nocturnal mammals spotted along with opportunistic sightings of other taxa. This resulted in 19 species recorded across 89 sightings, including African civet *Civettictis Civetta* and bushy-tailed mongoose *Bdeogale crassicauda*.

iNaturalist: iNaturalist is a digital citizen science platform to upload evidence-based wildlife observations. iNaturalist has been used across expeditions in VMWR enabling species diversity comparisons across years. In 2025, citizen scientists recorded 171 observations of 109 species. Birds were the most recorded taxa followed by mammals. Since 2022, birds have remained the taxa with the highest number of records. Observations and number of species peaked in 2022 at 389 and 154, respectively, with 2025 seeing the second highest numbers for each of these categories.

CHIYAMBI

Mu Seputembala 2024 ndi 2025, asayansi a nzika za Biosphere Expeditions' adathandizira kafukufuku wopangidwa ndi Lilongwe Wildlife Trust (LWT) ku malo otetezedwa a Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve (VMWR) kwa chaka chachisanu ndi chisanu ndi chimodzi kuyambira 2018 (kupatula zaka za COVID 2020 ndi 2021) Lipoti lophatikiza la 2024/2025 limapereka zambiri pamaulendo onse asanu ndi limodzi kuti awone kusintha kwachilengedwe mu VMWR.

Zotsatira zakafukufuku zapachaka za Biosphere Expedition zakhala zothandiza kwambiri pakuwunika zamoyo zosiyanasiyana komanso chiwelengelo cha nyama zikuluzikulu mu malo otetezedwa a Vwaza. Chiwelengele cha njobvu chikuwoneka chokhazikika ndipo sichikupita kukadya mbeu kumaminda. Chiwerengero cha mvuu chatsika kwambiri m'zaka zisanu ndi chimodzi zapitazi ndipo zifukwa za kuchepa kumeneku ziyenera kufufuzidwa ndi njira mogwilizana ndi a Nyika-Vwaza Co-Management Trust (NVCMT). Ulendowu mpaka pano wangokhala gulu limodzi kapena angapo m'nyengo yachilimwe yokha. Nzoyenela kuti tibwerezenso kafukufukuyi mu nyengo zina, mwina kawiri pachaka, kuti tiwone momwe zotsatira zingakhalire mu nyengo zina. Zotsatira zamagulu zinali motere

Kuwona chiwelengelo cha njovu komanso kutolera ndowe zake: M'Malawi monse, mkangano pakati pa anthu ndi Njovu, Makamaka zikatuluka m'malo otetezedwa ndikulowa m'madera kapena m'minda zakhala chiwopsezo chowonjezereka ku miyoyo ya anthu. Izi zikupangitsanso chiwopseza ku njovu zomwe zimatuluka kukadya mbewu kuminda. Mu 2021, mpanda unamangidwa m'malire akumwera ndi kum'mawa kwa Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve (VMWR) pofuna kuteteza njovu mkati mwa malo otetezedwawa. Mu 2025 nzika za sayansi zidaona njobvu ka 38 ndipo zinawelenge njovu zokwana 323 (4 zazimuna ndi magulu 34) mkati mwa VMWR. Izi zinali zotsika poyerekeza ndi zaka zambiri zam'mbuyomu kupatula mu 2023. Komabe, asayansi a nzika adawonjezeranso ID imodzi yatsopano ya njovu ku buku la zizindikilo za njovu ya LWT ndikusintha ma ID atatu omwe analipo. Ndowe zokwana 146 za njobvu zinasonkhanitsidwanso kuti awunike ngat mungapezeke njere za mbeu zakumunda ndipo Palibe umboni wa kadyedwe ka mbewu womwe wapezeka, ngakhale malipoti aposachedwa akuti njovu zikuchoka pakiyo kutuluka panja analipo. Izi zinali zogwirizana ndi zaka zapitazo.

Chiwerengero cha Mvuu: Mano a mvuu ndi magwero a minyanga ya njovu, zomwe zimapangitsa kuti nyamayi ikhale yosavuta kupha nyama. Mkati mwa VMWR, Nyanja ya Kazuni ndi chigawo chakumwera kwa mtsinje wa Rukuru ndi malo okhawa omwe amakhala ndi madzi chaka chonse ndipo amasunga chiwerengelo cha Mvuu. Kuziyang'anira mvuu pa kuwunika kwapachaka kwa Biosphere Expeditions' ndikofunikira kwambiri. Pakafukufukuyu mphepete mwa kumpoto kwa Nyanjayi inayendedwa maulendo asanu ndi limodzi, zomwe zinachititsa kuti mvuu 502 ziwerengedwe. Chiwerengero chachikulu kwambiri cha ulendo umodzi chinali 114. Chiwerengero cha mvuu chaonetsa kutsika kwambiri makamaka mu chaka cha 2018 ndi 2019 ndipo mu chaka cha 2024 chiwelengelochi chinali chotsika kwambiri. Chiwerengelo Chakwera kuchoka mu chaka cha 2024. Zifukwa za kutsika kwa chiwerengelochi sikunadziwiikebe

Kuika makamera: Kutchela makamera ndi njira yomwe imagwilitsidwa ntchito Poyang'anila nyama yosazisokoneza posaziyandikila makamaka ku nyama zomwe zili zovuta kupeza komanso zamanyazi. makamera 14 anatcheledwa pakafukufukuyi mmisewu yaku mpoto komanso nseu waukulu mu nkhalangoyi. Makamera asanu ndi chimodzi anaikidwa malo omwe amaonetsa kuti nyama zimadutsamo kwambiri makamaka tinjira take, m'mphepete mwa nyanja ndi bwalo la ndege. Makamerawa anajambula zithunzi zokwana 2835 zinali ndi nyama zamitundu 24 ndipo mvuu zinali ndi zithunzi zambiri (zithunzi 972 pazithunzi 95). Mitundu ina yodziwika bwino inali akambuku, serval komanso nkhandwe. Zotsatira za kafukufukuyi sizinasiyane kwenikweni ndi zaka za mbuyomu ndipo mitundu ya nyama yomwe inajambulidwa sinasiyanenso.

Bird transects: Mbalame ndi chizindikiro chabwino kwambiri cha thanzi la chilengedwe chonse, makamaka mbalame zam'madzi. M'mbuyomu VMWR yakhala ikuyang'anira kusiyanasiyana kwa mbalame, koma zolemba sizinasinthidwe posachedwapa koterokuti ntchitoyi idawonjezedwa kuti isinthe zolemba. Kunayendedwa maulendo anayi m'mbali mwa kumpoto kwa nyanjayi ndipo kunaonedwa mbalame mitundu 42 pa mbalama 82 zomwe zinaonedwa.

Maulendo a usiku: Nyama zoyenda usiku ndizovuta kuyang'anila kwake. Kuonjezela kutchela ma kamera, Azakafukufuku za sayansi anapanga maulendo oyendetsa kumwera kwankhalango ya VMWR kanayi mammawa ndi usiku kuti athandizile kuyang'ana nyamazi. Pamaulendowa akaona nyama zikuyenda amalemba mmabuku za mtundu komanso nthawi yomwe awonela. Iwowa anaona nyama mitundu 19 pa nyama 89 zomwe anaona.

iNaturalist: iNaturalist ndi tsamba la digito lomwe limagwilitsidwa ntchito ndi azasayansi kuika zithunzi za nyama munthu ukajambula. tsambali linagwilitsidwa ntchito mu mzaka zonse za kafukufukuzi. Mu 2025, asayansi nzika adalemba ndikujambula ka 171 pa mitundu 109 ya nyama. Mbalame ndizomwe zinaonedwa kwambiri motsogozana ndi nyama zikuluzikulu zoyamwitsa. Kuyambira 2022, mbalame zakhala zomwe zimaoendwa kwambiri. Nyama zambiri zinaonedwa mu chaka cha 2022 ndipo zinaonedwa ka 389 ndi 154, motsatana, pomwe 2025 idawona ziwerengero zachiwiri zapamwamba kwambiri pagulu lililonse lamagulu awa.

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1. Expedition Review

Matthias Hammer (editor)
Biosphere Expeditions

1.1. Background

Background information, location conditions and the research area are as per [Harwood et al. \(2019\)](#). The citizen science expedition in Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve (VMWR) in northern Malawi focused on biodiversity surveying. All data contributed to a long-term dataset and monitoring programme in VMWR and the larger Malawi-Zambia Transfrontier Conservation Area. The report will be shared with the Nyika-Vwaza Co-Management Trust (NVCMT) to empower and influence effective conservation strategies.

1.2. Dates & teams

The expeditions ran for one 14-day group from 1 – 13 September 2024 and one 14-day group from 6 – 19 September 2025 and comprised two teams of national and international citizen scientists, professional scientists and an expedition leader. Dates were chosen to coincide with the dry season in Malawi and its corresponding ease of access to the reserve and wildlife sightings.

The expedition teams were recruited by Biosphere Expeditions and consisted of a mixture of ages, nationalities and backgrounds. They were (in alphabetical order and with country of residence):

2024: Wendy Astill (UK), Yvonne Barnes (UK), Janet Bellairs (UK), Susan Carter (USA), Neil Goodall (UK), Pam Gregory (UK), Kathy Haan (USA, blogger, see her [blog](#) and [video](#)), Glory Muva (Malawi, [placement](#)), Jana Walther (Germany), Andrea Waschek (Germany), Sanne Wesselman (Netherlands, blogger, see her [blog](#)).

2025: Rita Adrian (Germany), Francesco Bellezza-Quarter (Italy), Jörg Dutz (Germany), H. Ulrich Göringer (Germany), Frank Heßler (Germany), Karen Janowitz (USA), Debbie Jones (UK), Hans-Uwe Mergener (Belgium), Debra Munding (USA), Ulrich Palmer (Germany), Joachim Schäfer (Germany), Louise Smith (Canada), Claire Thomsett (Austria).

On-site LWT field scientists and staff were: Dr Leandra Stracquadanio (Head of Biodiversity Research, Lilongwe Wildlife Trust, 2024 and 2025), Chimwemwe Kalulu Mponda (Research Technician, 2024 and 2025), Wanangwa Phiri (Research Technician, 2024), Gideon Banda (Volunteer Manager, 2025).

The expedition leader was Roland Arnison (2024 and 2025), joined in 2025 by assistant leader Simon Thomsett (trainee leader).

1.3. Partner

The Lilongwe Wildlife Trust (LWT) was established in 2009 and has grown into one of Malawi's leading conservation NGOs. LWT's mission is to save wildlife, deter nature crime, and secure healthy landscapes for people and wildlife in Malawi. Working in collaboration with local and international partners, the Trust responds to urgent conservation challenges and drives long-term social and institutional change. LWT has over 100 staff working across two sites in Lilongwe and several field sites across the country. The Government of Malawi has appointed LWT to administer several national wildlife management and conservation justice programmes. LWT is also a member of the International Union for Conservation of Nature, the Malawi representative for the Species Survival Network, and the Secretariat for the Malawi Parliamentary Conservation Caucus.

1.4. Acknowledgements

We are very grateful to all the expedition citizen scientists, who not only dedicated their spare time to helping but also, through their expedition contributions, funded the research. We would also like to thank our key partners, the Department of Parks and Wildlife (DNPW) and the Nyika-Vwaza Co-Management Trust for supporting our programme and assisting with local expertise, logistics and of course assistance from the park manager, research team and wildlife rangers. We would like to thank Elephants for Africa (EfA) for developing the elephant research protocols. Biosphere Expeditions would also like to thank members of the Friends of Biosphere Expeditions and donors for their sponsorship. Many thanks to the LWT team: Leandra Stracquadiano, Chimwemwe Kalulu Mponda and Gideon Banda for leading the research activities, the Operations and Placements teams for organising the in-country logistics and making the expedition a reality, and to Luka and Khumbo for producing wonderful meals and looking after the group at camp.

1.5. Further information & enquiries

More background information on Biosphere Expeditions in general and on this expedition in particular including pictures, diary excerpts and a copy of this report can be found on the Biosphere Expeditions website www.biosphere-expeditions.org. Enquiries should be addressed to Biosphere Expeditions at the address given on the website. Also available are:

All expedition reports, including this and previous expedition reports:

<https://www.researchgate.net/lab/Biosphere-Expeditions-Matthias-Hammer>

Expedition diary/blog:

<https://blog.biosphere-expeditions.org/category/expedition-blogs/malawi-2024/> (2024)

<https://blog.biosphere-expeditions.org/category/expedition-blogs/malawi-2025/> (2025)

Pictures, videos, media coverage of the expedition:

<https://www.biosphere-expeditions.org/malawi>

1.6. Expedition budget

Each citizen scientist paid a contribution of €2,980 (2024) and €2,990 (2025) per person per 13-day period towards expedition costs. The contribution covered accommodation and meals, supervision and induction, special research equipment and all transport from and to the team assembly point. It did not cover excess luggage charges, travel insurance, personal expenses such as telephone bills, souvenirs etc., or visa and other travel expenses to and from the assembly point (e.g. international flights). Details on how this contribution was spent are given below.

	2024	2025
Income	€	€
Expedition contributions	19,673	38,869
 Expenditure		
Base camp includes board & lodging and all services	11,925	15,963
Transport includes hire cars, fuel, taxis and other in-country transport	2,758	3,490
Equipment & hardware includes research materials & gear etc. purchased internationally & locally	523	1,256
Staff includes local and Biosphere Expeditions staff salaries and travel expenses	3,962	7,228
Administration includes miscellaneous fees & sundries	36	68
Team recruitment Malawi As estimated % of annual PR costs for Biosphere Expeditions	9,769	11,223
 Income – Expenditure	 -9,229	 -359
 Total percentage spent directly on project	 147%*	 101%*

*expedition operated at a loss and was supported by income from other expeditions

2. Elephant herd sightings

Leandra Stracquadanio
Lilongwe Wildlife Trust

2.1. Introduction & methods

The rationale, background, and methods for this study are unchanged from Hintz and Hammer (2023), which includes herd counts and the creation of elephant ID profiles.

2.2. Results

The 2025 expedition recorded 38 elephant observations (Table 2.2a). Of these, 34 were herds and 4 were lone bulls. This resulted in a total of 323 elephants counted throughout the survey period. The mean size of a herd or group with at least one adult female was 9 (standard deviation [SD] \pm 8.4; range 2 - 35). Elephants were encountered every day over the 14-day period apart from one. Sixteen observations were recorded from base camp, 22 were recorded from a vehicle.

The results of the 2024 and all other expeditions are shown in Table 2.2a.

Figure 2.2a. Observation locations of all elephants recorded during the 2025 expedition.

Throughout the six expeditions since 2018, 205 elephant observations have been recorded (Figure 2.2b – 2.2f; Table 2.2a). Eighty-six of these were recorded from base camp, with 113 from a vehicle, four on foot and three from nearby tourist chalets. 141 observations were in floodplain habitat, 54 in woodland, and 11 in grassland. Most sightings throughout the expedition years took place on the northern shore of Lake Kazuni, with many from the expedition base camp.

The total number of elephants recorded on each transect did not differ significantly across the years (Kruskal–Wallis H test: $\chi^2(5) = 9.26$, $p = 0.099$).

Table 2.2a. Summary of all elephant observations recorded throughout all expeditions in VMWR. It was not always possible to determine age class accurately, so categories represent those individuals where it was possible to assess age.

Year*	Total observations	Total number of elephants	Number of herds	Number of solitary bulls	Number of juveniles/infants	Mean herd size \pm SD
2018	38	616	35	3	78	17.5 \pm 17.8
2019	26	478	24	2	117	19.8 \pm 20.6
2022	42	457	28	14	135	15.8 \pm 16.8
2023	22	218	17	5	52	12.8 \pm 11.2
2024	39	445	35	5	181	12.9 \pm 11.8
2025	38	323	34	4	102	9.0 \pm 8.4

*No expeditions during COVID years 2020 and 2021.

Figure 2.2b. Cluster analysis of all elephant observations from six expeditions across 2018-2025 in VMWR. Clusters were calculated with a 200 m radius from the point of observation. Orange circles indicate the number of observations at that location.

Figure 2.2c. Total elephant sightings recorded during each expedition year.

Figure 2.2d. Breakdown of elephant age classes recorded during each expedition year, for individuals whose ages could be assessed. Infants/juveniles (≤ 10 years), subadults (11-15 years) and adults (≥ 16 years).

Figure 2.2e. Proportion of elephant age classes observed, cumulative across all expeditions. Infants/juveniles (≤ 10 years), subadults (11-15 years) and adults (≥ 16 years).

Figure 2.2f. Annual observations of the number of elephant herds and solitary bulls observed. Mean herd size is also displayed with a trendline.

Of the 323 elephants recorded in 2025, 70.3% had their age class accurately recorded. Of these, 31.8% (n = 94) were adults, comprising the main age class recorded. This was followed by 14.9% juveniles (n = 44) and 10.5% (n = 31) subadults.

In 2025, one new identification profile was added to the existing LWT elephant database and three previous profiles were updated to include new distinguishable features.

2.3. Discussion

Population trends of the VMWR elephants have not been comprehensively studied. The last six expeditions 2018-2025 have therefore contributed significantly to bridging this knowledge gap. Elephant populations are challenging to assess due to their long birth intervals (3 – 7 years) and gestation periods (22 months; Hanks and McIntosh 1973). Reproduction does not typically begin for a female until year seven, whereas males may reach reproductive age between 12 and 22 (Buss and Smith 1966). Therefore, there can be a delay in determining population trends and assessing threats or mortality rates. Previously, little was known about the elephant populations of VMWR, but since data collection began in 2018 there are now insights for the herds in the southern region of VMWR.

The predominant age class in the 2025 expedition aligned with previous years, showing mostly mature individuals. However, the rate of infants and juveniles was higher in 2024 compared to other years. The period 2018 – 2022 had the highest overall population levels recorded, with a large unexplained dip in 2019 and 2023. 2024 and 2025 both recorded lower numbers than the earlier expedition years. This shifted again in 2024 with a large increase, which then decreased again in 2025. The notable year-to-year changes in elephant population counts are unexplained and indicate that closer monitoring is necessary. Elephants may be travelling further into the reserve in search of resources and may be spending less time around the expedition site. This may also contribute to the reduction in mean herd size recorded across the years.

These expeditions are the only herd counts that occur each year. Ideally elephant counts would be conducted seasonally to investigate how e.g. water and food availability may affect the Vwaza herds. Previously, aerial surveys of the game in VMWR have been conducted sporadically. In 2013, the elephant population was estimated at 310 individuals which then decreased to 203 in 2015 (Macpherson 2015). However, it is challenging to compare population numbers from these expeditions to the previous aerial counts. The expeditions focus around Lake Kazuni and it is not possible to monitor the entirety of the lake at once for unique individuals. Many of the counts that took place were noticeably of reoccurring herds since any surrounding herd relies on the lake for water every one to two days (Kerley et al. 2008). Further aerial count surveys are recommended in conjunction with expedition herd observations throughout different seasons. This can be done via fixed-wing aircraft or drone surveys. A thermal drone was briefly trialled for elephant detection during the 2025 expedition and can be deployed in future expeditions.

2.4. Outlook for future expedition work

Elephant population monitoring is a vital yet challenging part of protected area management. It can be difficult to establish population health without long-term data, which these expeditions are now contributing to. It will be essential going forward to continue and expand on these surveys using mixed methodology such as aerial counts and in different seasons. This will provide a more comprehensive understanding of herd structure and movements.

2.5. Literature cited

Buss, I. O. and Smith, N. S. (1966) Observations on Reproduction and Breeding Behavior of the African Elephant. *The Journal of Wildlife Management*. Vol 30(2), pp. 375-388.

Hanks, J., and McIntosh, J. E. A. (1973) Population dynamics of the African elephant (*Loxodonta africana*). *Journal of Zoology*. Vol. 169(1), pp. 29–38.

Hintz, B. and Hammer, M. (2023) From elephants to cats to butterflies: Monitoring biodiversity of Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve, Malawi. Expedition report for expedition Sep/Oct 2022. [DOI 7969227](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-389227), accessed 26 June 2024.

Kerley, G. I. H., Landman, M., Kruger, L., Owen-Smith, N., Balvour, D., de Boer, W. F., Gaylard, A. Lindsay, K. and Slotow, R. (2008) Effects of Elephants on Ecosystems and Biodiversity. In: Mennell, K. G. and Scholes, R. J. (ed). *The 2007 scientific Assessment of Elephant Management in South Africa*. Pretoria: CSIR, pp. 101-147.

Macpherson, D. (2015) Report on an aerial wildlife census of Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve, Malawi – October 2015. Unpublished, Department of National Parks and Wildlife. Malawi.

3. Elephant dung sampling

Leandra Stracquadanio
Lilongwe Wildlife Trust

3.1. Introduction

The rationale, background, and methods for this study are unchanged from [Hintz and Hammer \(2023\)](#).

3.2. Results

In 2025, 146 boli from 27 elephant dung samples and in 2024, 115 boli were collected from 23 samples and assessed for seed presence to determine if cultivated crops were being consumed by elephants. No crop seeds were found in any of the dung boli and very few seeds overall were found (n = 219 seeds from 18 samples). All seeds extracted were from natural vegetation from inside the protected area. Most dung boli were retrieved from the northern side of Lake Kazuni, within 1.5 km of base camp (n = 14 samples; Figure 3.2a). This is a key area for human-wildlife conflict and the primary area where boli assessment is necessary. Historically, before the fence was erected in 2021, this area had high instances of elephants exiting the reserve.

Figure 3.2a. Collection locations of elephant dung boli during the 2025 expedition. The park boundary is where the fence was erected in 2021.

3.3. Discussion

Dung sampling in VMWR provides useful insights into the dietary ecology of elephants within VMWR. Across all dung samples collected in 2024 and 2025, none contained seeds from cultivated crops. This result of no cultivated seeds is consistent with 2022 (n = 196 boli) and 2023 (n = 153 boli). Data throughout the expedition years therefore strongly indicates that the fence is effective in keeping elephants inside the reserve and thereby reducing human-elephant conflict.

In 2025, very few seeds were found in the boli overall, although the number of boli collected remained relatively similar across expedition years. Most dung samples were collected around Lake Kazuni, as this is the only permanent water source during the dry season. Elephants rely on this lake due to their high dependence on water, meaning they must access this source at least every one to two days (Kerley et al. 2008). During the dry season, elephants are therefore predominantly seen around Lake Kazuni, and it can be challenging to locate them in other areas of the reserve - as noted on previous expeditions. Due to this, most boli samples were collected around the lake, less than 1.5 km from base camp, and should represent diets across a range of elephant herds (Sievert et al., unpublished). Elephant digestion time is approximately 12 hours, therefore only foraging during the expedition period could be evaluated.

Since 2022 no cultivated seeds have been found in elephant boli during the expeditions. The southern region of VMWR has been fully fenced since 2021, although elephants are capable of breaking out of such fences. One incident of human-elephant conflict was reported during the 2025 expedition. However, this was not in the expedition region of VMWR. As no crop seeds were detected across the two-week period, it is likely that elephants in the expedition area were not foraging on cultivated foods at this time. However, some crops do not produce easily detectable seeds, such as bananas. To assess elephant crop foraging levels in the southern VMWR region, dung monitoring is an effective method for some common crop types, such as maize.

3.4. Outlook for future expedition work

Although the fence seems to be working, elephants can easily create holes in it or overcome it by other methods. Therefore, dung monitoring should continue annually and if possible across different seasons when different crops are ripe to provide evidence of any crop raiding to support ongoing human-elephant coexistence initiatives.

3.5. Literature cited

Hintz, B. and Hammer, M. (2023) From elephants to cats to butterflies: Monitoring biodiversity of Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve, Malawi. Expedition report for expedition Sep/Oct 2022. [DOI 7969227](#), accessed 26 June 2024.

Kerley, G. I. H., Landman, M., Kruger, L., Owen-Smith, N., Balvour, D., de Boer, W. F., Gaylard, A. Lindsay, K. and Slotow, R. (2008) Effects of Elephants on Ecosystems and Biodiversity. In: Mennell, K. G. and Scholes, R. J. (ed). The 2007 scientific Assessment of Elephant Management in South Africa. Pretoria: CSIR, pp. 101-147.

Sievert, O., Sankhani, P. and Hintz, B. (unpublished) Using elephant pathways and dung to investigate human-wildlife conflict around Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve. NVT Final Grant Report 2022.

4. Hippo count transects

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4.1. Introduction

The rationale and background for the hippo transects are unchanged from [Hintz and Hammer \(2023\)](#).

4.2. Results

In 2025, six 5 km transects were completed along the northern side of Lake Kazuni up to the eastern end where the lake connects to the South Rukuru River (Figure 4.2a and Figure 4.2b). Over the expedition period, 502 hippos were recorded with a mean of 84 per transect. The mean size of a pod was 3.5 (SD \pm 3.9; Table 4.2a). Counts were recorded at similar points along the transect across expeditions (Figure 4.2c).

The data for 2024 are shown in Table 4.2a, alongside data from all other expedition years 2018-2025.

Figure 4.2a. Locations of all hippo observations recorded during the 2025 expedition.

Figure 4.2b. Kernel density hotspot map of hippo locations recorded during the 2025 expedition.

Figure 4.2c. Kernel density hotspot map of all transect locations where hippos were observed from 2018, 2019, 2022, 2023, 2024 and 2025.

There was a significant decrease between the hippo counts recorded during each transect across expedition years (Kruskal–Wallis H test: $\chi^2(5) = 20.43$, $p = 0.001$; Dunn’s test with Bonferroni correction ($\alpha = 0.0033$). An overall decline over time was recorded; mean transect counts more than halved between 2018 and 2024.

Table 4.2a Summary of the hippo observations recorded across six years of expeditions. An asterisk denotes when values have been averaged by number of expedition groups because more than one group took place in a single year. Age class and pod size data are not available for 2019. Age class represents the individuals where identification was possible. It was not always possible to assess the age of every animal.

Year†	Number of animals	Number of adults	Number of juveniles or infants	Mean pod size (\pm SD)	Range of observation size	Mean count per transect (\pm SD)	Range of total count per transect
2018 (3 groups)	885*	569*	48*	7.9 \pm 10.4	1 - 76	153 \pm 66.5	56 - 336
2019 (2 groups)	686*				1 - 40	124 \pm 38.2	28 - 168
2022	698	595	87	4.6 \pm 4.9	1 - 26	96 \pm 23.9	89 - 159
2023	446	301	57	3.3 \pm 3.5	1 - 23	112 \pm 23.5	78 - 133
2024	394	256	95	3.5 \pm 3.1	1 - 17	65 \pm 17.5	44 - 87
2025	502	218	45	3.5 \pm 3.9	1 - 25	84 \pm 20.6	68 - 114

†No expeditions during Covid years 2020 and 2021.

4.3. Discussion

The 2024 and 2025 hippo surveys showed that hippos are continuing to spend more time towards the South Rukuru River end of Lake Kazuni. This appears to be a trend since 2022 indicating that areas of high hippo use and grazing are likely centred away from the woodland habitat surrounding Lake Kazuni and the areas closer to base camp.

During the 2025 expedition, 502 hippos were recorded in total. This was relatively consistent with 2023 and 2024, but lower than 2022. Over time, there has been a decrease in the average number of hippos recorded over each transect and there was a significant drop in hippo populations since 2018. The range of hippo pod size recorded throughout each transect in each single year has also dropped, as has the mean pod size after 2019. This indicates a concerning trend for the hippo population in VMWR, which appears to have halved between 2018 and 2024 (Figure 4.2d).

Figure 4.2d. Number of hippos counted during each transect in 2018, 2019, 2022, 2023, 2024 and 2025. The 2018 expedition consisted of three groups, 2019 of two groups and all other expeditions of one group.

Since each expedition has taken place in Malawi's dry season, hippos are likely travelling further within their territories to search for resources as there is little vegetation available near the lakeside, possibly indicating a restriction on resources or other push factors. They then travel back to the lake as the main available water source. This may differ during the wet season when vegetation is more plentiful. The dry season also means temperatures are higher and thus hippos spend more time in the water during the day to regulate body temperature before foraging at night (Lewison and Pluháček 2017). Core areas are likely the main lake waterbody with utilisation of smaller tributaries of the South Rukuru River depending on resource availability and season. Changes in habitat usage may be seasonally caused by water level shifts with less water available in the dry season. To assess this, seasonal (if possible) or annual water levels should be recorded along with vegetation availability. This could possibly be included in future expeditions by utilising habitat mapping via drone.

These results indicate that further research is required to determine the reason for this decline and assess if anthropogenic factors such as human-wildlife conflict or ivory poaching are the drivers, or whether some other factors related to habitat change, lack of resources or disease are the underlying cause. However, it is important to note that areas along the South Rukuru River to the west are inaccessible by car or on foot, so population assessments are not possible there. So it is possible that hippos are occupying a different range, which is contributing to or causing the decline in observations at accessible points. Aerial drone surveys may be useful in future expeditions to survey otherwise inaccessible areas.

4.4. Outlook for future expedition work

A clear decline in population levels of hippos along Lake Kazuni from 2018 – 2025 has been determined. The monitoring of hippos therefore continues to be a priority in VMWR and the NVCMT can utilise these results to support a more detailed understanding of this trend and to implement conservation strategies where necessary.

4.5. Literature cited

Hintz, B. and Hammer, M. (2023) From elephants to cats to butterflies: Monitoring biodiversity of Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve, Malawi. Expedition report for expedition Sep/Oct 2022. [DOI 7969227](https://doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.20172.RLTS.T10103A18567364), accessed 26 June 2024.

Lewison, R. and Pluháček, J. (2017). Hippopotamus amphibius. The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2017: e.T10103A18567364. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.20172.RLTS.T10103A18567364.en>. Accessed on 05 January 2023. National Parks and Wildlife Act (2017). Part IX, sections 73-75.

5. Camera trapping

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5.1. Introduction

The rationale and background for this study are unchanged from [Hintz and Hammer \(2023\)](#).

5.2. Methods

In 2025, 20 infrared camera traps (Bushnell, Spartan and iZeeker) were deployed throughout the southern area of VMWR. 14 were set at sites utilised over previous expeditions along the southern and northern roads, approximately 2 km apart (Figure 5.2a). An additional six were set at opportunistic locations along the lakeside and airstrip, targeting locations of high animal use, such as mammal paths. For one night, one opportunistic camera was moved to a Helmeted guinea fowl carcass located during other research activities. The camera was moved back to its original location after that night. The cameras were fixed to trees between 60 – 90 cm above the ground facing either the road or a target habitat feature. Camera settings were standardised as much as possible across all cameras: 16MP image size, 10 second intervals, medium sensitivity and medium shutter speed.

Figure 5.2a. Camera trap deployment locations during the 2025 expedition.

The cameras were deployed on the first day of the expedition, checked after seven days, and collected after 12 days. All pictures were analysed using [Timelapse2](#) (v2.3.0.0). Only pictures containing animals were included in the analysis. Capture events were defined at two-minute intervals and any images of the same species within these two minutes are considered part of the same capture. Camera trap data analysis utilised capture events rather than number of images.

5.3. Results

The data for 2024 are shown in Table 5.3b, alongside data from all other expedition years 2018-2025.

In 2025, 264 camera trap nights resulted in 18,758 images. 336 capture events recorded 24 species across 2,835 animal photos (Table 5.3a). Of these, 21 species are listed by the IUCN as “Least Concern” (Figure 5.3b). Elephants are listed as “Endangered”, hippos and leopard as “Vulnerable”.

Table 5.3a. Species captured on camera traps during the 2025 expedition. IUCN Red List status is displayed. LC = least concern, NT = near threatened, VU = vulnerable, EN = endangered

Common Name	Scientific Name	IUCN Red List status	Total images	Total captures
Ungulates				
African elephant	<i>Loxodonta africana</i>	EN	158	26
Cape Buffalo	<i>Syncerus caffer caffer</i>	LC	146	3
Common duiker	<i>Sylvicapra grimmia</i>	LC	8	5
Greater kudu	<i>Tragelaphus strepsiceros</i>	LC	72	13
Harnessed bushbuck	<i>Tragelaphus scriptus</i>	LC	16	11
Hippopotamus	<i>Hippopotamus amphibius</i>	VU	972	95
Impala	<i>Aepyceros melampus</i>	LC	873	38
Warthog	<i>Phacochoerus africanus</i>	LC	47	5
Carnivores				
African civet	<i>Civettictis civetta</i>	LC	20	17
Bushy-tailed mongoose	<i>Bdeogale crassicauda</i>	LC	10	5
Honey badger	<i>Mellivora capensis</i>	LC	3	1
Large-spotted genet	<i>Genetta maculata</i>	LC	6	2
Leopard	<i>Panthera pardus</i>	VU	1	1
Serval	<i>Leptailurus serval</i>	LC	2	1
Side striped jackal	<i>Lupulella adusta</i>	LC	1	1
Spotted hyaena	<i>Crocuta crocuta</i>	LC	2	2
Primates				
Vervet monkey	<i>Chlorocebus pygerythrus</i>	LC	46	26
Yellow baboon	<i>Papio cynocephalus</i>	LC	280	44
Other mammals				
African savanna hare	<i>Lepus victoriae</i>	LC	14	8
Cape porcupine	<i>Hystrix africaeaustralis</i>	LC	5	4
Elephant shrew		LC	3	2
Birds				
Collared flycatcher	<i>Ficedula albicollis</i>	LC	1	1
Emerald-spotted wood-dove	<i>Turtur chalcospilos</i>	LC	5	1
Helmeted Guinea fowl	<i>Numida meleagris</i>	LC	144	24
Total			2835	336

Figure 5.3b. IUCN Red List status of the species captured on camera traps during the 2025 expedition.

It is noteworthy that in 2025 camera traps recorded three species not previously captured by camera trap: side striped jackal, emerald-spotted wood-dove and collared flycatcher. Bushy-tailed mongoose was also detected, which had previously only been recorded once in 2023. A total of 47 species have been recorded on expedition camera traps since 2018 with 2550 capture events (Table 5.3b).

The number of capture nights across years varied (156 – 544) but this did not significantly influence the number of species detected (linear regression: slope = 0.039, $p = 0.32$), showing that camera trapping effort did not impact detections. The overall number of species detected did not significantly differ across years (linear regression: slope = -0.16 , $p = 0.93$; Figure 5.3c). The most frequently captured species across years included elephants, hippos, yellow baboons, helmeted-guinea fowl and vervet monkeys, which stayed largely consistent in 2025 along with the addition of impalas (Figures 5.3d – 5.3f).

Figure 5.3c. On the left axis, number of camera trap nights (effort) used in each expedition year. For 2018, this covers three groups and in 2019 this covers two groups; all other years comprised one group. The number of species detected each year is displayed on the right axis.

Table 5.3b Species captured on camera traps during all expeditions 2018 - 2025. IUCN Red list status is displayed. LC = least concern, NT = near threatened, VU = vulnerable, EN = endangered. In 2018 the expedition comprised three groups, in 2019 two groups. All other years comprised one group and there were no expeditions during the COVID years 2020 and 2021.

Species	Scientific name	IUCN status	2018	2019	2022	2023	2024	2025	Total captures
Ungulates									
African elephant	<i>Loxodonta africana</i>	LC	67	177	33	140	11	26	454
Bush pig	<i>Potamochoerus larvatus</i>	LC	3	0	7	0	0	0	10
Cape Buffalo	<i>Syncerus caffer caffer</i>	LC	4	71	13	0	0	3	91
Common duiker	<i>Sylvicapra grimmia</i>	LC	20	30	2	2	0	5	59
Greater kudu	<i>Tragelaphus strepsiceros</i>	LC	18	13	11	3	1	13	59
Hippopotamus	<i>Hippopotamus amphibius</i>	VU	28	141	139	25	2	95	430
Harnessed bushbuck	<i>Tragelaphus scriptus</i>	LC	37	46	9	0	0	11	103
Impala	<i>Aepyceros melampus</i>	LC	12	27	22	2	0	38	101
Puku	<i>Kobus vardonii</i>	NT	1	0	0	6	0	0	7
Sharpe's grysbok	<i>Raphicerus sharpei</i>	LC	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
Roan antelope	<i>Hippotragus equinus</i>	LC	3	3	3	0	0	0	9
Warthog	<i>Phacochoerus africanus</i>	LC	10	48	3	10	1	5	77
Carnivores									
African civet	<i>Civettictis civetta</i>	LC	37	0	23	23	1	17	101
African wild cat	<i>Felis lybica</i>	LC	5	6	0	0	0	0	11
African wild dog	<i>Lycaon pictus</i>	EN	0	0	4	0	0	0	4
Banded mongoose	<i>Mungos mungo</i>	LC	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
Bushy-tailed mongoose	<i>Bdeogale crassicauda</i>	LC	0	0	0	1	0	5	6
Caracal	<i>Caracal caracal</i>	LC	7	9	0	0	0	0	16
Ichneumon mongoose	<i>Herpestes ichneumon</i>	LC	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
Honey badger	<i>Mellivora capensis</i>	LC	23	9	18	2	0	1	53
Large-spotted genet	<i>Genetta maculata</i>	LC	49	9	11	7	1	2	79
Leopard	<i>Panthera pardus</i>	VU	3	3	1	8	0	1	16
Lion	<i>Panthera leo</i>	VU	4	0	0	0	0	0	4
Marsh mongoose	<i>Atilax paludinosus</i>	LC	13	3	1	0	0	0	17

Species	Scientific name	IUCN status	2018	2019	2022	2023	2024	2025	Total captures
Selous's mongoose	<i>Paracynictis selousi</i>	LC	0	0	1	2	0	0	3
Serval	<i>Leptailurus serval</i>	LC	6	9	0	0	0	1	16
Side striped jackal	<i>Lupulella adusta</i>	LC	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Slender mongoose	<i>Galerella sanguinea</i>	LC	6	0	0	0	0	0	6
Spotted hyaena	<i>Crocuta crocuta</i>	LC	20	10	13	15	2	2	62
White-tailed mongoose	<i>Ichneumia albicauda</i>	LC	7	0	1	1	0	0	9
Primates									
Greater bushbaby	<i>Otolemur crassicaudatus</i>	LC	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Vervet monkey	<i>Chlorocebus pygerythrus</i>	LC	18	44	4	22	0	26	114
Yellow baboon	<i>Papio cynocephalus</i>	LC	55	214	32	13	2	44	360
Other mammals									
Aardvark	<i>Orycteropus afer</i>	LC	2	0	0	0	0	0	2
African savanna hare	<i>Lepus victoriae</i>	LC	18	0	14	6	1	8	47
Cape porcupine	<i>Hystrix africaeaustralis</i>	LC	22	13	11	11	0	4	61
Elephant shrew		LC	3	7	0	8	0	2	20
Birds									
Cape turtle dove	<i>Streptopelia capicola</i>	LC	2	0	0	0	0	0	2
Collared flycatcher	<i>Ficedula albicollis</i>	LC	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Emerald-spotted wood-dove	<i>Turtur chalcospilos</i>	LC	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
European bee-eater	<i>Merops apiaster</i>	LC	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Fiscal flycatcher	<i>Sigelus silens</i>	LC	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Grey hornbill	<i>Lophoceros nasutus</i>	LC	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Helmeted Guinea fowl	<i>Numida meleagris</i>	LC	26	6	67	0	0	24	123
Lilac-breasted roller	<i>Coracias caudatus</i>	LC	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
Southern ground hornbill	<i>Bucorvus leadbeateri</i>	VU	1	0	3	0	0	0	4
Spotted eagle owl	<i>Bubo africanus</i>	LC	0	3	0	0	0	0	3
Total			533	901	447	309	23	336	2550

Figure 5.3d. Ungulate species detected by camera trap across all expeditions 2018-2025.

Figure 5.3e. Carnivore species detected by camera trap across all expeditions 2018-2025

Figure 5.3f. Primate, other mammal or bird species by camera trap across all expeditions 2018-2025

Appendix 1 shows the diversity of species detected by camera traps during the 2024 and 2025 expeditions.

5.4. Discussion

In 2025, species diversity recorded on camera traps increased compared to 2023 and 2024 and three new species were recorded: side-striped jackal, emerald-spotted wood-dove and collared flycatcher. Overall results are consistent across all expedition years, with elephants, hippos and yellow baboons most commonly captured. Several elusive species including leopard, serval and honey badger were also recorded in 2025. These carnivores are not captured every year therefore their presence in 2025 indicates that they are resident in VMWR. By contrast, wild dogs were not detected in 2023 – 2025, indicating that the images recorded during the 2022 expedition were likely of transient visitors that are not resident in VMWR (Sievert et al. 2023). 2024 recorded a low instance of large carnivores with spotted hyaena only captured twice. In general, 2024 had a low diversity of captured species compared to other years, probably because of dense vegetation present at the camera sites, which made it more challenging to detect wildlife via camera trap. In 2025, park management undertook controlled burning prior to the expedition, therefore wildlife was much easier to detect.

Despite the notable variation in the number of images recorded throughout the years over a range of camera trap nights, the difference between the number of species detected year-to-year was not statistically significant. It is useful to note, therefore, that camera trapping effort at the current level enables accurate diversity monitoring. Multiple expedition groups were run in 2018 and 2019, which accounts for the larger number of camera trap nights and overall captures in those years. In 2025, six cameras were placed strategically on mammal paths, assuming these would capture higher levels of activity. This assumption was correct and cameras captured more animal images per trap night than most other cameras and enhanced the diversity of data collected.

5.5. Outlook for future expedition work

Camera trapping is an excellent cost-effective, non-invasive and straightforward tool to measure biodiversity, presence, and species distribution across a variety of habitats. It also has the potential to estimate relative abundance or population levels of some species. Cameras can be placed strategically or randomly and can document data throughout the entire day over a long period of time. This means their uses are very diverse and they can play a crucial role in biodiversity monitoring. For future expeditions, the set-up should include targeted placements as in the 2025 expedition to maximise image captures.

5.6. Literature cited

Hintz, B. and Hammer, M. (2023) From elephants to cats to butterflies: Monitoring biodiversity of Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve, Malawi. Expedition report for expedition Sep/Oct 2022. [DOI 7969227](https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.10671), accessed 26 June 2024.

Sievert, O., Hammer, M., Comley, E., Hintz, B., Mgoola, W. O., & Davis, R. S. (2023). A novel record of African wild dogs (*Lycaon pictus*) in Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve, Malawi. *Ecology and Evolution*, 13, e10671. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.10671>

6. Bird Transects

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6.1. Introduction

Bird transects were introduced for the first time on the 2025 expedition.

Avian species, particularly aquatic species, are established indicators of ecosystem health (Gregory and Van Strien 2010, Tabur and Ayvaz 2010). Over the last three decades, global bird diversity has been in decline (Lees et al. 2022). Broadly, the presence of birds in a habitat is linked to food web dynamics and heavily influenced by water and habitat quality. Bird diversity is an early indicator of nutrient status in the environment and environmental degradation (Tabur and Ayvaz 2010). The floodplain-woodland habitat of VMWR along Lake Kazuni is an ideal area of the reserve to investigate bird diversity as a proxy for ecosystem stability. Aquatic species are particularly sensitive to changes in the environment such as eutrophication or pollution (Gregory and Van Strien 2010, Newman et al. 2007), whereas woodland/terrestrial species are indicators of vegetation structure, disturbance levels and resource availability (Debus et al. 2017).

Bird surveys are commonly used to monitor ecosystem health and biodiversity, because birds are relatively easy to detect by sight or sound, occupy diverse niches, and are sensitive to environmental change (Debus et al. 2017, Gregory and Van Strien 2010, Newman et al. 2007). Birds as a group occupy several trophic levels through their diverse diets of insects, seeds, fish and meat. They contribute to pollination and seed control, thus their presence or absence can shift ecosystem functioning (Anderson et al. 2016). The monitoring of birds as indicator species is important to provide essential context for adaptive management and conservation strategies in VMWR.

The diversity of bird species in VMWR has not been comprehensively assessed. The most recent scientific report is from 2009 (Engel et al. 2013) and listed 394 known bird species in the reserve. Since then, sporadic bird surveys have been conducted by park management, but these have not taken place regularly, thus detailed information on the overall bird diversity within the reserve is lacking.

6.2. Methods

During the dry season in VMWR, both aquatic and terrestrial bird species are concentrated around Lake Kazuni as the primary water source in the reserve. Therefore, the expedition conducted bird diversity surveys along the lake floodplain. Bird transects were conducted on four days, non-consecutively. A team of up to six individuals departed base camp at 05:30 to maximise the peak activity hours of birds. Three transects began at base camp and were carried out for 90 minutes on the flood plain between the lake and the woodland. The fourth transect was started further along the lakeside where the previous transect ended.

Observers paused each time a bird was seen and recorded the species and number of individuals. During each observation the location, time, compass angle and perpendicular distance from the observer (90°) were also recorded. Birds were determined to be separate observations if there were at least 20 metres between individuals. An expert birder led the group and identification books were consulted throughout the data collection process. If the species remained unknown, photographs were taken and the species was identified back at base camp. All species were uploaded to the iNaturalist online platform (see chapter 8).

6.3. Results

Forty avian species were recorded over four transects in 85 sightings (Figure 6.3a/b, Table 6.3a). Fifteen of these were primarily wetland/aquatic dwelling species and 25 were predominantly terrestrial species. Terrestrial species were recorded in more areas along the transect, whereas - as can be expected - wetland/aquatic species were concentrated in key areas on the lake or along the lakeshore (Figure 6.3c).

Figure 6.3a. Distribution of bird observation points during all bird transects. If numerous species were present in the same recording location, the same GPS coordinates were recorded.

Figure 6.3b. Total number of bird species and individuals counted during each transect.

Table 6.3a. All species and counts recorded during the four bird transect surveys in 2025.

Species	Scientific name	Primary habitat	Total individuals recorded
African grey hornbill	<i>Lophoceros nasutus</i>	Terrestrial	22
African sacred ibis	<i>Threskiornis aethiopicus</i>	Wetland/aquatic	1
Arrow-marked babbler	<i>Turdoides jardineii</i>	Terrestrial	6
Black collared Barbet	<i>Lybius torquatus</i>	Terrestrial	1
Black-headed oriole	<i>Oriolus larvatus</i>	Terrestrial	1
Blacksmith lapwing	<i>Vanellus armatus</i>	Wetland/aquatic	9
Black-winged stilt	<i>Himantopus himantopus</i>	Wetland/aquatic	2
Blue waxbill	<i>Uraeginthus angolensis</i>	Terrestrial	1
Canary species	<i>Serinus / Crithagra spp.</i>	Terrestrial	1
Common Boubou	<i>Laniarius ferrugineus</i>	Terrestrial	3
Common Bulbul	<i>Pycnonotus barbatus</i>	Terrestrial	1
Common Sandpiper	<i>Actitis hypoleucos</i>	Wetland/aquatic	5
Egyptian goose	<i>Alopochen aegyptiaca</i>	Wetland/aquatic	9
Emerald spotted wood dove	<i>Turtur chalcospilos</i>	Terrestrial	3
Fish eagle	<i>Haliaeetus vocifer</i>	Wetland/aquatic	1
Gabar goshawk	<i>Micronisus gabar</i>	Terrestrial	1
Glossy ibis	<i>Plegadis falcinellus</i>	Wetland/aquatic	3
Goliath heron	<i>Ardea goliath</i>	Wetland/aquatic	1
Great egret	<i>Ardea alba</i>	Wetland/aquatic	1
Green wood hoopoe	<i>Phoeniculus purpureus</i>	Terrestrial	4
Grey heron	<i>Ardea cinerea</i>	Wetland/aquatic	6
Helmeted Guinea fowl	<i>Numida meleagris</i>	Terrestrial	47
Kittlitz's plover	<i>Charadrius pecuarius</i>	Wetland/aquatic	6
Lesser marked weaver	<i>Ploceus intermedius</i>	Terrestrial	5
Pied kingfisher	<i>Ceryle rudis</i>	Wetland/aquatic	2
Plover species	<i>Charadrius spp.</i>	Wetland/aquatic	5
Red-eyed dove	<i>Streptopelia semitorquata</i>	Terrestrial	1
Red-necked falcon	<i>Falco chicquera</i>	Terrestrial	1
Ring-necked dove	<i>Streptopelia capicola</i>	Terrestrial	22
Slender-billed weaver	<i>Ploceus pelzelni</i>	Terrestrial	3
South fiscal	<i>Lanius collaris</i>	Terrestrial	1
Southern Tchagra	<i>Tchagra australis</i>	Terrestrial	1
Tropical Boubou	<i>Laniarius aethiopicus</i>	Terrestrial	3
Warbler species	<i>Acrocephalus / Phylloscopus spp.</i>	Terrestrial	4
Water thick knee	<i>Burhinus vermiculatus</i>	Wetland/aquatic	1
White-crested helmet shrike	<i>Prionops plumatus</i>	Terrestrial	10
Wood dove	<i>Turtur / Streptopelia spp.</i>	Terrestrial	1
Yellow-bellied greenbul	<i>Chlorocichla flaviventris</i>	Terrestrial	1
Yellow-billed stork	<i>Mycteria ibis</i>	Wetland/aquatic	1
Yellow-breasted canary	<i>Lophoceros nasutus</i>	Terrestrial	8
Total			205

Figure 6.3c. Distribution and kernel heat density of wetland/aquatic species records (top) and terrestrial species records (bottom).

6.4. Discussion

A diverse range of bird species was recorded during the 2025 expedition. A total of 42 species were observed, 16 wetland and 26 terrestrial species. Wetland birds tended to aggregate in specific areas along the lakeside and floodplain, whereas terrestrial species were recorded throughout most of the transect length, indicating a wider ecological niche.

Wetland and aquatic bird species are known to be sensitive to environmental changes; however, the presence of fish eagles and herons indicates the lake habitat remains healthy. Presence of the yellow-billed stork and goliath heron, which are relatively elusive, also indicates good water quality and health. The most frequently observed birds were the terrestrial species helmeted guinea fowl, African grey hornbill and ring-necked dove. These species are highly mobile and common species which explains their wide distribution.

These observations underscore the role of birds as biodiversity and ecosystem health indicators. The diversity here likely indicates that the habitats surrounding and including Lake Kazuni are in good health. However, this should be assessed annually to monitor population and biodiversity trends.

6.5. Outlook for future expedition work

Bird surveys in 2025 added to the breadth of biodiversity data collected throughout the expedition and provided a positive indication of ecosystem health levels. However, this must be compared annually to fully understand if ecosystem health is changing over time. These surveys can now be used as a baseline to be used by the NVCMT and others to assess changes in subsequent years and across seasons. Continuing bird surveys in future expeditions will ensure the inventory of bird species in VMWR is kept up to date and avian diversity and population trend estimates over subsequent years will contribute to assessments of overall biodiversity and ecosystem changes.

6.6. Literature cited

- Anderson, S. H., Kelly, D., Robertson, A. W., & Ladley, J. J. (2016). Pollination by birds. *Why birds matter: avian ecological function and ecosystem services*, 73.
- Debus, S. J., Martin, W. K., & Lemon, J. M. (2017). Changes in woodland bird communities as replanted woodland matures. *Pacific Conservation Biology*, 23(4), 359-371.
- Gregory, R. D., & Van Strien, A. (2010). Wild bird indicators: using composite population trends of birds as measures of environmental health. *Ornithological Science*, 9(1), 3-22.
- Engel, J. I., Bates, J. M., Weckstein, J. D., Gnoske, T. P., & Kaliba, P. M. (2013). Avifauna of Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve, Malawi. *Journal of East African Natural History*, 101(2), 223-240.
- Lees, A. C., Haskell, L., Allinson, T., Bezeng, S. B., Burfield, I. J., Renjifo, L. M., ... & Butchart, S. H. (2022). State of the world's birds. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 47(1), 231-260.
- Newman, S. H., Chmura, A., Converse, K., Kilpatrick, A. M., Patel, N., Lammers, E., & Daszak, P. (2007). Aquatic bird disease and mortality as an indicator of changing ecosystem health. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 352, 299-309.
- Tabur, M. A., & Ayvaz, Y. (2010, June). Ecological importance of birds. In *Second International Symposium on Sustainable Development Conference* (pp. 560-565).

7. Night Transects

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7.1. Introduction

Night transects were introduced for the first time on the 2025 expedition.

To add to the robustness of the biodiversity data collected throughout the expedition, the expedition conducted night transects targeting elusive mammal species. This activity was complementary to camera trapping data and iNaturalist observations to collect a more complete dataset of the species present in VMWR (Fournier and Kremetz 2017, Hart et al. 2022). Many species of ecological significance are challenging to detect during the day or via opportunistic sightings (Gaston 2019). This can cause cryptic, shy or elusive species to be underrepresented in biodiversity datasets, such as birds of prey or mesocarnivores (Gaston 2019).

By adding night transects as a research activity, the expedition aimed to bridge any data gaps. Unlike camera traps, which are placed at fixed locations for a period of time, night transects enable semi-targeted searches in habitats or areas that are not completely viewable by camera effort (Fournier et al. 2017, Hart et al. 2022). Driven night transects mean larger areas can be covered in a safe way. The transects also allow for the observers to use sight and sound to detect movement, vocalisations or eye-shine, which may be less common or harder to detect during daylight hours (Scott et al. 2005). Overall, this activity aimed to enhance long-term biodiversity datasets within VMWR by supporting the detection of additional, elusive species.

7.2. Methods

Transects were undertaken by vehicle one hour after sunset at approximately 19:30 and lasted between 2 – 3 hours. All transects started and ended at base camp. Routes included the floodplain road along Lake Kazuni, the east-west primary road within the park, and the northern road to the airstrip. A specific transect route was not set, instead routes to maximise coverage across the transects were used. While driving, white spotlights were used by citizen scientists to locate animals with eye-shine. When eye-shine was detected, the vehicle stopped and a red filter was applied to the spotlight to minimise disturbance to the animal. Observers also listened for vocalisations and movement sounds throughout the transects to aid locating fauna.

During a transect, when an animal of any species was observed, this was recorded along with the number of individuals. Mammals were prioritised during the drives, but non-mammalian species were also recorded opportunistically. GPS location and time of sighting were recorded. The GPS location of the car was used to approximate the animal's location, rather than recording perpendicular distance and bearing. Individuals were observed closely to ensure they were not double counted if they moved.

7.3. Results

Three night transects and one opportunistic early morning transect were conducted during the expedition. These resulted in 89 observations of 18 species and 260 individuals (Table 7.3a, Figure 7.3a/b). Of these, three species (spotted eagle owl, owl spp and toad spp), were not recorded during any other expedition activity. These three species were also the only non-mammal species recorded (Figure 7.3c).

Table 7.3a All species observations recorded during the night transect activity.

Species	Scientific name	Count
Bushbaby	<i>Galago spp.</i>	14
Bush pig	<i>Potamochoerus larvatus</i>	1
Bushy tailed mongoose	<i>Bdeogale crassicauda</i>	1
Civet	<i>Civettictis civetta</i>	1
Elephant	<i>Loxodonta africana</i>	15
Harnessed bushbuck	<i>Tragelaphus scriptus</i>	11
Large-spotted genet	<i>Genetta maculata</i>	2
African savanna hare	<i>Lepus victoriae</i>	26
Hippo	<i>Hippopotamus amphibius</i>	12
Impala	<i>Aepyceros melampus</i>	142
Greater kudu	<i>Tragelaphus strepsiceros</i>	24
Mongoose	<i>Herpestidae spp.</i>	1
Mouse	<i>Mus spp.</i>	1
Owl spp	<i>Strigiformes spp.</i>	1
Puku	<i>Kobus vardonii</i>	2
Spotted eagle owl	<i>Bubo africanus</i>	1
Toad	<i>Bufoidea spp.</i>	2
Vervet	<i>Chlorocebus pygerythrus</i>	3

Figure 7.3a. Points at which observations were recorded during the 2025 night transects.

Figure 7.3b Number of observations per species on night transects.

Figure 7.3c. Taxonomic groups recorded during night transects.

7.4. Discussion

The night transect activity contributed to the biodiversity dataset during the 2025 expedition by yielding observations of several non-mammalian species not otherwise recorded through other activities: spotted eagle owl, an unknown owl species and an unknown toad species. Although night transects targeted mammals, they only produced two species unobserved via camera trap: bush pig and a mouse species. Overall, over 250 individual animals of 18 species were recorded.

Although a low number of unique species was recorded, the quantity of individuals and number of observations each provide information on nocturnal animal behaviour and where these animals are concentrated at night. Large numbers of impala along the lakeside were recorded, possibly due to the safety of the open floodplain, which allows the animals to see approaching predators more easily. The behavioural insights, distribution data and information on group numbers mean this activity resulted in valuable ecological data, which complemented other expedition data and resulted in multiple observations of species not recorded through other activities.

7.5. Outlook for future expedition work

Night transects should continue as an activity for future expeditions with planned routes and survey timeframes. In 2025, routes aimed to maximise coverage; however, repeated transects may yield a more standardised result. Overall, this activity provided insights into bushbaby distribution, impala night-time behaviour and biodiversity data for other nocturnal species, which would not otherwise have been collected.

7.6. Literature cited

Fournier, A. M., & Krementz, D. G. (2017). Nocturnal distance sampling all-terrain vehicle surveys for nonbreeding rails. *Wildlife Society Bulletin*, 41(1), 151-156.

Gaston, K. J. (2019). Nighttime ecology: the “nocturnal problem” revisited. *The American Naturalist*, 193(4), 481-502.

Hart, A. G., Dawson, M., Fourie, R., MacTavish, L., & Goodenough, A. E. (2022). Comparing the effectiveness of camera trapping, driven transects and ad hoc records for surveying nocturnal mammals against a known species assemblage. *Community Ecology*, 23(1), 27-39.

Scott, D. M., Waite, S., Maddox, T. M., Freer, R. A., & Dunstone, N. (2005). The validity and precision of spotlighting for surveying desert mammal communities. *Journal of Arid Environments*, 61(4), 589-601.

8. iNaturalist

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8.1. Introduction

[iNaturalist](#) is a long-standing biodiversity monitoring platform, which was developed in 2008 and later partnered with the California Academy of Science and National Geographic. It is a community and citizen science project that allows anyone globally to upload sightings of any taxa. iNaturalist acts as a biodiversity social media platform to collect evidence-based observations and allows other users to confirm or identify species to achieve research grade sightings. Any form of evidence can be uploaded to the platform including sightings, camera trap images, spoor, dung, feathers or leaves. Each upload is classed as an observation and once an observation is confirmed as a specific taxa by three users, it is upgraded to “Research Grade”. If an upload cannot be identified to species level, the platform allows broader classes such as orders to be used. All sightings are publicly available and can be used by researchers worldwide.

LWT has utilised iNaturalist in several projects since 2022 to generate a record of species found in Malawi and in VMWR. It is an invaluable tool, which has led to the cataloguing and identification of numerous species across LWT’s research sites.

8.2. Methods

The methods for this study are unchanged from [Hintz and Hammer \(2023\)](#).

A project “Biosphere Malawi 2025 Biodiversity Monitoring” was created on iNaturalist and all uploads were added to this project. If a species was only recorded by camera trap, this was also uploaded to the platform.

8.3. Results

This activity in 2025 recorded 171 observations of 109 species throughout the expedition. Of these, 95 (55.6%) observations reached “Research Grade” level (Table 8.3a). 52 bird species were recorded, which comprised the taxa group with the most observations (47.3%; Figure 8.3a). This was followed by mammals with 24 species (21.8%) and then insects with 15 species (13.6%). Four species which were not directly observed were uploaded from the camera trap data: leopard, serval, jackal and honey badger.

Data for the 2024 expedition are shown in Table 8.3a, alongside data for all other expedition years 2022-2025.

Table 8.3a. Summary of iNaturalist data submitted during each expedition 2022-2025.

Year	Observations	Species	Research Grade
2022	389	154	190
2023	144	100	112
2024	153	91	76
2025	171	109	95
Total	857	454 cumulative	473 cumulative

Figure 8.3a. Data submitted to iNaturalist during the 2025 expedition by taxonomic group.

Throughout all years, birds remained the primary taxa recorded, followed consistently by either mammals or insects. A lesser diversity of plants, arachnids, reptiles, amphibians, molluscs and fish were recorded across most expeditions (Figure 8.3b).

Figure 8.3b. Data submitted to iNaturalist by the expeditions, by year and taxonomic group.

8.4. Discussion

iNaturalist has been utilised as an expedition tool for four consecutive years in VMWR. It continues to demonstrate the value of using citizen science observations to document biodiversity, especially when coupled with ecological survey techniques. Birds were consistently the most recorded taxa group year on year, followed by mammals and insects. Overall, 857 observations have been logged throughout the years, with 454 cumulative species.

2022 saw the most observations and species recorded with a substantial decline in 2023, due to the previous invertebrate sampling activity not continuing after 2022. However, between 2023 and 2025, numbers remained relatively stable. In 2024 and 2025, species richness increased to include additional taxa groups such as fish, amphibians and molluscs. This change can be attributed to changing expertise across the researchers and differences in the interests of the citizen scientists. The flexibility of the platform to include spoor evidence meant that the expedition was able to record the presence of lions through the sighting of a lion track. Additionally, the expedition uploaded an opportunistic observation of a roan antelope. Neither species was recorded on the camera traps, so iNaturalist enabled this data to be collected in an alternative way. This is particularly important as lions are not known to be resident in Vwaza, but rather are transient visitors from Zambia. In 2018 four camera trap captures of lions were recorded during the expedition (Harwood et al. 2019) - and lions have not been recorded since during Biosphere Expeditions projects, but may have been recorded opportunistically by VMWR rangers. Overall, the 2025 expedition's iNaturalist activity contributed to the long-term biodiversity dataset for VMWR and enhanced the diversity of the existing species catalogue.

8.5. Outlook for future expedition work

iNaturalist is an easy to use, powerful application for recording and assessing biodiversity data. It has the additional benefit of observations being reviewed by experts and scientists anywhere in the world to achieve 'Research Grade' and ensure a robust dataset. Year-to-year comparisons of species presence in VMWR from iNaturalist data has provided important insights into overall biodiversity and thus it is recommended that this activity continues in future expeditions. Data are publicly available so act as an open access tool for researchers and other stakeholders anywhere in the world.

8.6. Literature cited

Harwood, A., Stone, E. Shevlin, K. and Hammer, M. (2019) From elephants to cats to butterflies: Monitoring biodiversity of Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve, Malawi. Expedition report for expedition Sep/Oct 2018. [DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20265.83046](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20265.83046), accessed 26 June 2024.

Hintz, B. and Hammer, M. (2023) From elephants to cats to butterflies: Monitoring biodiversity of Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve, Malawi. Expedition report for expedition Sep/Oct 2022. [DOI 7969227](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.7969227), accessed 26 June 2024.

Loarie, S. (2022). iNaturalist – What is it? Available at: <https://www.inaturalist.org/pages/what+is+it>. Last accessed on 18 December 2023.

9. Discussion and conclusions

Since 2018, the data collected during the annual Biosphere Expeditions projects in VMWR has been invaluable in monitoring biodiversity and megafauna population levels. This report comparatively assessed data across all expedition years to conclude that overall biodiversity in VMWR is high. This high diversity comprises a high number of bird species as well as mesocarnivores, insects, primates and elephants.

Elephant populations were found to be stable and not consuming cultivated crops, which may indicate that human-wildlife conflict levels in the southern region of the reserve have decreased. However, incident reports and data from the NVCMT should be assessed to fully evaluate this.

Notably, hippo populations in Lake Kazuni have dramatically declined over the past six years. This may be due to hippos travelling further to search for food and other resources, or potentially due to other factors such as disease, habitat changes, poaching for ivory, or a combination of these and other pressures. This finding and expedition results can now be used by NVCMT to develop management strategies.

Overall, the data presented here are a valuable contribution to longitudinal monitoring of the ecosystem health of southern VMWR. Bird and elephant surveys, camera trapping and iNaturalist all contributed to a holistic assessment of biodiversity.

The expedition so far has been limited to one or more groups during the dry season. It is recommended to replicate the expedition work during other seasons, potentially bi-annually, to assess seasonality of these results.

Appendix 1: Selection of camera trap images captured in 2024 and 2025.

Warthog (2024)

Spotted hyaena (2024)

M

87F31C

09-05-2024 15:55:25

Banded mongoose (2024)

M

100F38C

09-06-2024 14:09:08

Bushbuck (2024)

Hippopotamus (2024)

African savannah hare (2024)

African elephant (2024)

Bushy-tailed mongoose (2025)

Bushnell M 75F24C 09-12-2025 19:21:38
African elephants (2025)

Bushnell M 74F 23C 09-14-2025 22:41:09
Spotted hyaena (2025)

Hippopotamus (2025)

African leopard (2025)

Cape porcupine (2025)

African civet (2025)

Honey badgers (2025)

Serval (2024)

Cape buffalo (2025)

White-tailed mongoose (2025)